

ET systems: a high-level approach to additive synthesis control

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an algorithmic strategy based on network systems for controlling the large number of parameters typically implied in the additive synthesis process. Such an approach relies on the definition of the behaviour of a system, of which the generated parametric control is an emergent property. This method descends from observations on the behaviour of vibrating acoustic bodies, which constitute both an inspiration and a starting point for developing the control paradigm.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the light of Fourier theory, the timbre of musical instruments can be considered as consisting of multiple harmonic and non-harmonic partials or overtones [1]. Additive synthesis is a sound production technique exploiting this principle to generate complex timbres by superimposing sine waves of different frequencies and amplitudes. The power of additive synthesis derives from the fact that is theoretically possible to closely approximate any complex waveform as a sum of elementary waveforms [2]. Given the large number of time-variant attributes, additive synthesis features a disadvantageous input/output complexity ratio compared to other synthesis techniques. Moreover, manipulating the synthesis parameters is not always obvious, from a musical perspective [3] [4]. The multitude of additive synthesis parameters is often addressed with high-level algorithmic control structures and spectral processes [3] or simplified by partial grouping techniques [5] [6] and data approximation methods [7] [8].

This paper proposes a method based on network systems to exert high-level control over additive synthesis parameters. Such a systemic approach allows to manage a large corpus of synthesis attributes from a global viewpoint, providing parametric control as an emergent property of the system. The design of such a control structure descends from observations on the behaviour of vibrating acoustic bodies, exploited as a starting point for the development of the control paradigm.

These network systems, together with some specific tools useful for their control, are implemented as a collection of external objects named *et* for the Max 8 environment¹.

¹ <https://cycling74.com>

2. GENERAL METHODOLOGY

2.1 Overarching design principles

In order to successfully address the heavy demand for control data, the proposed method for managing additive synthesis parameters has to comply with the following:

- It must determine the state of multiple parameters at the same time.
- It must retain the same level of input complexity independently of the number of parameters it is used to control.
- It must provide values for the parametric control; these values may vary over time and such variations must be autonomous to a certain degree.
- The interactions with the control system must be as simple and minimal as possible.

Some of the aforementioned requirements are well addressed by another sound synthesis technique: physical modelling synthesis. Physically modelled instruments are defined by a small number of geometrical and material parameters, and are played by sending to them physically meaningful data such as striking locations and forces, or blowing pressures [9]. Moreover, such techniques rely on the definition of the behaviour of a system of which the generated waveforms are an emergent property. This approach, which we can categorize as a *systemic* one, directly addresses issues of control, making the complexity implicit.

The proposed method translates the systemic approach to the control of additive synthesis parameters. Our approach does not implement a physical modelling method, nor it aims to replicate the acoustic phenomena of any physical sound source. The references to acoustic physics and physical modelling synthesis are purely metaphoric or instrumental in designing a synthesis control system which exhibits musically relevant behaviours.

2.2 Synthesis control through network systems

A network is a system consisting of many similar elements (*nodes*) linked by connections (*arcs*), so as to allow movement or communication among them. In a network system, the mutation of a part may determine, according to the scheme of connections, the variation of others. By applying this paradigm to synthesis parameters, we can vary a large number of those through localized interactions that

can create a complex chain of events. This makes network systems good candidates for successfully controlling many parameters from a high-level perspective, providing complex outcomes through simple interactions. We shall call the network systems designed to implement the proposed control method *et systems*, where *et* stands for ‘energy transfer’ — the reason for this specific terminology will be made clear over the next few sections.

3. OVERVIEW OF ET SYSTEMS

3.1 Significant observations on the behaviour of oscillating acoustic bodies

When a body with elastic properties is excited by an external force, it produces travelling waves that move back and forth and deform it. The interferences between such travelling waves lead to the generation of standing waves, responsible for specific sonic phenomena. Each oscillating body produces many simultaneous standing waves, namely its oscillatory modes.

The movement of the body occurs in the time domain but produces phenomena that are perceived and can be meaningfully described in the frequency domain. The amplitude variation of oscillatory modes is the result of interference between the aforementioned travelling waves, but it can be alternatively described as an energy transfer between oscillatory modes [10]. The proposed method exploits the energy transfer principle to control the amplitude of additive synthesis partials and their evolution over time.

3.2 What are *et* systems

et systems are network systems specifically designed to control additive synthesis parameters. Such systems can be conveniently described by weighted directed graphs. At each instant, each node contains a scalar value representing the amplitude of a partial. The arcs of the graph represent the connection towards one direction only and nodes are capable of totally or partially migrate the quantity they contain to other nodes through the arcs connecting them. With a somewhat inaccurate term, we shall call such quantity *energy*². A weight called *energy transfer factor* is assigned to each arc defining the amount of node-to-node transferred energy against time. Such energy transfers give rise to an evolution of the system, computable in a discrete-time domain.

The graph in Fig. 1, $k_{(from \rightarrow to)}$ shows the energy transfer factors as the weights of its arcs.

3.3 The adjacency matrix

Energy transfer factors can be conveniently expressed as adjacency matrices. We assume the following conventions to represent the arcs between nodes and the energy transfer factors in matrix form:

² The term ‘energy’ here must not be understood as the physical quantity, but rather as a scalar value that can be partly transferred over time from one node to another, similarly to what happens with actual energy in vibrating bodies according to the energy transfer model.

Figure 1. Weighted directed graph

- Each matrix cell contains an energy transfer factor (for readability’s sake, empty cells imply a factor of 0).
- A system of Cartesian coordinates ranging from 1 to the total amount of nodes identifies the transfer factors.
- In the coordinate system, x is the index of the emitting node, y is the index of the receiving node.
- An energy transfer factor other than 0, expressed in the relative matrix cell, establishes an arc between two nodes.
- An energy transfer factor expressed in the $x = y$ diagonal establishes an arc from the node to itself (that is, a loop).

Figure 2. Energy transfer factors as an adjacency matrix

3.4 Anatomy of *et* systems

In the simplistic transfer matrix in Fig. 3, in which a single arc has non-zero weight, the value assigned to $node_1$ in t is equal to the value of $node_2$ in $t - 1$ multiplied by the

Figure 3. A simplistic matrix. The arc connecting node 2 to node 1 is represented as a value in cell (2;1). In consequence, the value 0.8 present in node 2 at $t - 1$ is multiplied by 0.5 and transferred to node 1 at $t1$.

transfer energy factor located in the transfer matrix at coordinates (2; 1). This energy transfer is therefore expressed as:

$$node_{to}^t = node_{from}^{t-1} \cdot k_{(from;to)} \quad (1)$$

where $node_{to}$ is the receiving node, $node_{from}$ is the emitting node and $k_{(from;to)}$ is the transfer energy factor contained in the transfer matrix at cell coordinates $(from;to)$. t represents the current stage of system evaluation and $t - 1$ the previous one. In the described energy transfer system, it is also possible for multiple nodes to simultaneously transfer energy to a single target node.

Figure 4. Multiple nodes transferring energy to a single target node

For n emitting nodes, the energy transfer is therefore generally expressed as:

$$node_{to}^t = \sum_{from=1}^n node_{from}^{t-1} \cdot k_{(from;to)} \quad (2)$$

Namely, $node_{to}$ equals to the sum of the energy contained in the emitting nodes in $t - 1$ multiplied by the relative energy transfer factors.

In equation 2, when $from = to$ and $k_{from;to}$ is a non-null transfer factor, energy gets transferred from a node to itself. This, from a physical standpoint, can be interpreted as *inertia*, that is, the tendency of a body to maintain unaltered its state of motion. Inertia can be defined as an amount of energy a node can retain, or, in our formalism, give it back to itself at the next system evaluation stage. The amount of inertia is expressed by energy transfer factor located over the adjacency matrix diagonal.

Figure 5. Inertial transfer factor

Given an initial system state, the transfer matrix configuration determines therefore how the system evolves through subsequent evaluation stages.

So far, we only considered linear transfer between nodes, but the proposed system allows to specify custom, potentially non-linear transfer functions, which can be defined individually for every node. The non-linearity of transfers may concur to the creation of oscillating system behaviours and attack transients:

$$node_{to}^t = f_{to} \left(\sum_{from=1}^n node_{from}^{t-1} \cdot k_{from;to} \right) \quad (3)$$

Where $f_{to}(x)$ is the energy transfer function for node to .

Nodes	Init	t_1	t_2	t_3	t_4
$node_1$	0	2	0	8	0
$node_2$	1	0	4	0	16
$node_3$	0	2	0	8	0
$node_4$	1	0	4	0	16

Table 2. Exploding system behaviour

Figure 6. Example of subsequent stages of system evaluation

3.5 Controlling the amount of energy contained within the system

The systems described in the previous section require the injection of an initial amount of energy to observe a spontaneous evolution of the system in a discrete time domain. According to the adjacency matrix configuration, the initial values of the nodes and the energy transfer functions, the system may spontaneously evolve in different ways.

	0.5			
0.5				
			0.5	
		0.5		

Nodes	Init	t_1	t_2	t_3	t_4
$node_1$	0	0.5	0	0.125	0
$node_2$	1	0	0.25	0	0.0625
$node_3$	0	0.5	0	0.125	0
$node_4$	1	0	0.25	0	0.0625

Table 1. Dying system behaviour

	2			
2				
			2	
		2		

Tab. 1 and Tab. 2 show two possible behaviours of the system: using linear transfer functions $f(x) = x$ and initializing the nodes with the values reported in the tables, the amount of energy contained within the system tends to 0 for the system in Tab. 1, and to ∞ for the system in Tab. 2. As the values contained in the nodes are assigned to control amplitude parameters, it is crucial to prevent the energy contained within the system from extinguishing or exploding autonomously. This can be addressed by properly defining normalized energy transfer matrices, that is, ensuring the sum of the weights of each adjacency matrix column equals 1.

However, if the energy transfer functions differ from $f(x) = x$, normalized adjacency matrices alone do not prevent the system from the aforementioned issues. For such reasons, *et* systems are not controlled by injecting energy into the system from outside, but rather the values of the nodes are initialized as a small positive number close to zero³, and the energy contained within the system gets ‘expanded’ or ‘contracted’ by multiplying the values of the nodes by a given gain factor. By using multiplication for controlling the amount of energy, it is possible to ‘force’ the global energy of the system in t as a function of the amount of energy in $t - 1$ (see 3.6.2).

3.6 Controlling the evolution of the system

Bounding the behaviour of the system between arbitrary limits is crucial for its application as a control device. The evolution of *et* systems can be controlled in three ways, which will be described in the following paragraphs.

3.6.1 Clipping

Clipping functions, setting a limit to the values each node can take, can be defined for each node independently, and are meant to define the spectral profile of the synthesized sound.

$$node_{to}^t = c_{to} \left[f_{to} \left(\sum_{from=1}^n node_{from}^{t-1} \cdot k_{(from;to)} \right) \right] \quad (4)$$

Where $c_{to}(x)$ is the clipping function.

3.6.2 Targeting

A target level parameter for the system to fluctuate around can be set. It arbitrarily controls the point of equilibrium of the system by ‘expanding’ or ‘contracting’ the energy contained within it. This is accomplished by computing the

³ This value is 10^{-10} in the current software implementation.

overall energy level of the system for each instant of time and providing a gain factor in function of it to be applied to each node. The current energy level of the system is calculated as the sum of the absolute values of each node at a given instant t ; the gain factor is computed by dividing the target level for the current energy level. Each node value in $t + 1$ will be then multiplied by the resulting gain factor:

$$\text{current level} = \sum_{i=1}^n |\text{node}_i^{t-1}|$$

;

$$\text{gain} = \frac{\text{target level}}{\text{current level}} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{node}_{i_{to}}^t = c_{to} \left[\text{gain} \cdot f_{to} \left(\sum_{from=1}^n \text{node}_{from}^{t-1} \cdot k_{(from;to)} \right) \right] \quad (6)$$

The target level parameter allows the creation of amplitude envelopes.

3.6.3 Damping

A damping parameter can be expressed by gain factors. Such factors, different for each node, may interfere with the spontaneous system evolution by increasing or decreasing the values of nodes:

$$\text{node}_{i_{to}}^t = c_{to} \left[\text{damp}_{to} \cdot \text{gain} \cdot f_{to} \left(\sum_{from=1}^n \text{node}_{from}^{t-1} \cdot k_{(from;to)} \right) \right] \quad (7)$$

This control can be used to determine the resonant qualities of a system in compliance with rules other than the ones defined in the energy transfer matrix.

4. ET SYSTEMS AS CONTROL PARADIGM

Practically using the system first requires a definition stage in which the user defines the system behaviour by filling the transfer matrix and designing the energy transfer functions. Such definition is responsible for the spectral behaviour of the synthesized sound, that is, its spectral envelope and overall timbre. The nodes are initialized with a ‘small’ positive value close to 0. Once the matrix is defined, the system can be started: at each discrete instant of time, the values for all the nodes are calculated, based upon the values at the previous instant, the weights of the arcs and all the accessory considerations previously exposed (non-linear transfer functions, clipping, and damping). As stated above, the user can generate amplitude envelopes by setting the target level parameter, which expands or contracts the energy contained within the system accordingly.

4.1 Energy transfer matrix definition

By filling the matrix with transfer factors clustered in precise areas, it is possible to roughly determine the system behaviour and the resulting spectral shape. Filling horizontal areas of the matrix concentrates the energy of the system in the given node or group of nodes. Filling the

Figure 7. *et* systems workflow

transfer matrix diagonally, above or below the diagonal, generates a progressive displacement of the system energy; from higher nodes to lower ones (above the diagonal) or, conversely, from lower nodes to higher ones (below the diagonal). Transfer factors can be either positive or negative. Negative transfer factors are the representation of transferred energy in opposition of phase. An energy transfer matrix filled with same-sign transfer factors is remarkably stable; if the matrix contains both positive and negative transfer factors, it will more likely show an oscillatory behaviour.

4.2 Energy transfer functions definition

By defining the response to the incoming energy, each node can have a specific behaviour according to the overall energy amount contained within the system. Moreover, the discrimination of such behaviours for each node allows to represent transients: defining an exponential profile for the energy transfer functions of the lower indexed nodes provides a sort of ‘impedance’; as the system target level rapidly increases, lower indexed partials are ‘slower’ in their reaction, providing the sonic result of an attack transient.

4.3 Clipping functions definition

Clipping functions concur to the definition of the spectral shape of the synthesized sound. They play an essential role in the process of generating transients as well; by setting the energy transfer functions as described in the previous section, the energy contained within the system tends to migrate toward areas of lower impedance as the system target level rises. As the amplitude of higher partials increases, it reaches a point, determined by the clipping functions, where it cannot to expand further for lack of ‘headroom’. If the target level keeps increasing, energy is ‘forced’ to distribute among other partials. This occurrence, together with the proper definition of transfer functions, tends to create attack transients.

4.4 Damping factors definition

Damping factors provide a convenient form of interaction with *et* systems allowing to actively interfere with the system evolution while the energy transfer calculation is running. Such factors result suitable to define frequency-dependent resonant qualities of the system: each node contains a value which is interpreted as amplitude information; nodes do not contain any frequency information, neither absolute nor in form of ratio to a given fundamental.

This is essential to the generality of the system, and indeed the assignment of such information to the additive synthesis apparatuses is completely arbitrary and not related to *et* systems, which only provide amplitude parameters. Through damping factors, it is possible, for instance, to determine a different behaviour of the system in function of the frequencies assigned to the partials. This metaphorically allows to establish a mutual relation between a ‘vibrating body’ (the core of the *et* system) and a ‘resonator’.

5. ET SYSTEMS IMPLEMENTATION IN THE MAX 8 ENVIRONMENT

The synthesis control system was implemented as a collection of external modules designed for the Max 8 environment (Cycling ’74). The modules featured in the package consist of a set of externals (written in C) and abstractions (Max patches composed of externals and possibly other abstractions). Such modules are designed to implement the *et* systems principles and provide useful tools for the definition of transfer matrices and the controls related to the *et* systems usage. These objects operate on both audio signals and lists; the objects that manipulate digital audio signals make extensive use of the *MC* protocol⁴.

Of particular interest for the topics discussed in this paper is the *et.transmatrix* module (Fig 10), an abstraction implementing some practical tools designed to edit the weights contained in *et* adjacency matrices. *et.transmatrix* provides a graphical approach to the definition of energy transfer matrices through a set of procedural ‘brushes’ and image processing functions. The graphical and procedural approaches allow to retain a fairly constant complexity with respect to the definition of the transfer matrix, for any dimension it may assume. Some of the included editing functions are:

Harmonic and sub-harmonic brushes — tools designed to procedurally edit the transfer matrix by modifying the values contained in those cells whose *y* coordinates are in harmonic or sub-harmonic ratio with the selected cell

Cluster brushes — tools designed to edit the values contained in matrix cells within a certain radius from the selected one.

Per-row and per-column editing — a set of functions operating on specific rows and columns; such functions include gradient generators and ‘hand-drawing’ of the transfer factors (Fig. 11).

Macro editing functions — a set of functions operating on the whole matrix; such functions include gate (remove any transfer factor whose absolute value is less than a given threshold), harmonic and non-harmonic gain factors and gradient generators manipulating cells above and below the $x = y$ diagonal independently.

⁴ “MC” is a communication protocol introduced in version 8 of the Max environment, allowing to “wrap” multiple digital audio signals into a single patch chords.

et.transmatrix also allows to edit the transfer matrices by user defined procedural methods and to incorporate custom image processing functions designed with *Jitter* objects.

The modules are still in development and will be released under open source licence in the coming months.

6. SOUND SYNTHESIS EXAMPLES

We have produced a small set of sounds examples, to show some possible behaviours of *et* systems. Each sound is produced by an additive synthesis process with a bank of 10 sine waves as oscillators, whose amplitude is guided by an *et* system. The examples are completed with a spectral analysis, showing the magnitude of each partial as a function of time (Fig.8, 9). The examples can be downloaded at the following URL: <https://bit.ly/3d7mc55>

Figure 8. Spectrogram of sound example 1

Figure 9. Spectrogram of sound example 2

One of the authors (Marson) has composed a musical study aimed to investigate the expressive capabilities of additive syntheses processes controlled by *et* systems. The study was composed by generating a large corpus of sonic gestures, synthesized by additive synthesis with narrow-filtered bands of white noise as oscillators, and by assembling such sonic materials in an audio editing software⁵.

7. CONCLUSIONS, LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

This paper proposes a method to establish a high-level algorithmic control over additive sound synthesis parameters. Such a method descends from observations on the

⁵ Cubase 6.5, Steinberg.

Figure 10. et.transmatrix

Figure 11. et.transmatrix column editing mode

behaviour of vibrating acoustic bodies, exploited as a starting point for developing the control paradigm. The control system was implemented under the name *et* as a package of external objects for the Max 8 environment.

The collected results appear promising since the control paradigm appears to satisfy the initial requirements. The systemic approach addresses, for the most part, the complexity issues characterizing the additive synthesis parametrization. Besides, this control paradigm is almost completely unaffected by scalability problems in regards to the managing of large numbers of parameters, by retaining a high-level kind of user interaction. With the appropriate settings, the sounds produced by synthesis processes guided by the proposed control paradigm show interesting features, including timbral qualities reminiscing of acoustic instrument nuances.

This approach to additive synthesis control presents however some critical aspects:

- The demand for computational power grows exponentially. This represents an issue for real-time applications of the control paradigm.
- The system definition is purely empirical; no sound analysis process is used at the moment to help define the system behaviour.
- Under certain circumstances, being the control paradigm based on non-linear systems, it may behave unpredictably, and would thus need to be reset in order to work properly again. This potential risk makes the *et* control systems unreliable for real-time performance environments at the moment.
- The tools useful for the procedural definition of adjacency matrices are suitable to control additive synthesis processes in which the synthesized partials are in harmonic or quasi-harmonic ratio to a given fundamental. It is less clear how to employ them for controlling strongly non-harmonic partials.

Moreover, the efficiency of the system is far from being optimal, especially when a large matrix is employed. The worst-case class of complexity of the currently employed algorithm is $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$, and — because of the inherently interdependent nature of the computation — no parallelisation has been attempted, whereas this would be a very interesting possibility to investigate, as it would allow to make use of a larger amount of partials for the synthesis process and to use complex *et* systems in real-time. As the management of large *et* systems is computationally intensive, the development of *et* systems specifically oriented to the control of additive group synthesis should be taken into account, in order to increase the spectral complexity of the synthesized sounds while retaining a contained amount of nodes to manage. Moreover, it will be crucial to establish collaboration with a mathematician and/or a computer scientist, so as to evaluate if the formalism of the *et* systems can be expressed in a cleaner way and therefore simplified, thus hopefully leading to higher efficiency. The capabilities of *et* systems may be expanded to treat n -dimensional vectors, opening the possibility to the

control of multidimensional parameters with the same approach, but this would cause even higher computational requirements. Lastly, a detailed study on computer-assisted methods to describe *et* transfer matrices, ranging from factorization techniques to machine learning, should be conducted and, on the other hand, other applications of the system (for example as a tool for musical formalization) should be investigated.

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